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Humanizing Machine or Mechanizing Human

Artificial Intelligence: Issues & Perspectives

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Abstract: This paper attempts to grasp the immense growth especially in bio engineering and neuron technology. It insists to follow the religious and ecclesial insights and be cautious on dangers ahead on Humanizing Machine or Mechanizing Human. In the process of humanizing machine certainly human becomes mechanic and that is why we call them computer mechanics. Though they are mechanics they cannot go hungry while the computer does not require it. AI does not require any raw materials as such humans need everything. It's a human wonder how this AI enters into every field and takes control of the human beings in our time. Elon Musk says that it may act with super consciousness in the near future like human beings and warns people that AI is more dangerous and cause public risk at any time at any level. We are super humans while they become smarter super computer humans today. The ray of improvement is exponential. The neuron technology paves way for new era of super brain consciousness. This paper explores how AI technology should deal in multiple aspects of life today and the responsibility of thinkers.

Introduction

Humans function in both ways as humanizing machines or mechanizing human. AI is our daily task of human experience. When humans are addicted to computer coding and decoding of its engineering process they never come out of it because even to correct a full stop or comma you may have to spend even for a week. Similarly the same humans strive to make the machine behave like humans has to work for years and decades and that is what the Alexatoday. Either of them is fit for real and holistic humans. Humans are humans and machines are machines. Humans are living being and since computers are programmed by humans it can behave like humans and not fully human. For instance if you open up Alexa you can see lot of chips and wires where as human body is extremely puzzle. Now let us explore essential aspects of human, computer, science, AI, and religion interface and its boons and dangers.

Social and Religious Perspectives

According to the CCC the family becomes the original cell of the society where man and woman love and procreates life. Authority, stability and relationships in the family lay foundations for freedom, security and fraternity in the society. The members learn to take up the responsibility to care the young, old, handicapped, sick and poor. The family must be defended by appropriate social measures for the well-being of each member. Human society can be neither well-ordered nor prosperous unless it has legitimated with authority to preserve institutions for work and care for the good will of all its members (CCC, Article 2, 4, 1897, 2207-2208, 463,533, GS 47, 1) similarly technology must deal in this manner. On the contrary it divides, and increase uncertainties. As per the Vat II documents, anything that which is harmful to the human dignity must be forbidden specially with regard to embryo, human cloning, gene editing, abortion and contraceptives except medical exceptions. It demands 'the way of Christ' that

‘leads to life’; a ‘contrary way leads to destruction’ (CCC, 1691, 1970, 422) In the process of social evolution, we lack social awareness towards the globe and one another. Now, can AI bring social coherence in global culture?

It also rests on journalists, writers, producers, distributors, critics and all those who involved in communication. They have the power to direct mankind along a good path or in evil path. It means that in the gathering and in the publication of news the moral law and the legitimate rights and dignity of man should be upheld. All knowledge is not profitable, but on the other hand “love builds” (1Cor8:1, Vat II, IM, 1963, 263-265) Covid -19 had proved that technology can do nothing about it. Even then we are not afraid to destroy the earth and question God. We do utterly fail to comprehend the unattainable Being over us according to Kuruvilla Pandikattu (Pandikattu, 2015, 10-11) FABC First Plenary Assembly on evangelization in modern day Asia in 1974 set a path of evangelization leading to the creation of enculturation of local churches according to their language, values and aspirations in Asia and foster dialogue with churches and religion. So through this efficient process the Gospel message could be proclaimed and redeem people from the various technological clutches (ND, 442) Yuval Noah Harari delivered on a TED Talk that the AI technology and super computer consciousness will disrupt the human cognition and privacy.

Cognitive and Cosmology Perspectives

Human mind composed of neurons and sensors which carry signals from systemic body to the cerebral cortex of brain and information are passed and actions are done due to the neurons burning says Mathew Alper on the ‘God part of the Brain’ (Alper, 2001, 8) The human cognitive power gradually reveals various human issues specially by the technology like Sophia, Alexa, self-driving car, defense robots and other space x by Elon Musk. When scientists talk on technology Pope Francis talks on care for common home. Pope Francis says in *Laudato Si*⁹ to care for

common home where all of us are interconnected to the earth (ND, Laudato Si, 2015, 1148) while Dalai Lama's Conversation in 2021 with scientists was great global concern. The universe expands enormously and the unknown dark energy creates uncertainty for our future. Due to cosmic war, we will have no pure air to breathe and pure water to drink in the future. According to Sacred Scripture we are called to till the earth and master over the earth (Gen1:28) Now we allow computers to master over and destroy the humans, earth and the whole cosmos. The human discoveries must never allow dehumanize the person. We are called to exercise our freedom for self-realization which is to become authentically human. Science, religion and technology must be at the service of the human kind. Science without conscience can lead to human's ruin (DV, 1965, Intro 2 & 4, GS.12, DH1) so gradually we lack ethical consciousness to protect and safeguard cosmos.

Evolution and Philosophy

The universe expands and AI technology develops into greater speed. Harari Reveals the Real Dangers Ahead | the TED Interview on August 9, 2022. He narrates how the history evolved from different stories of fascism, classism, liberalism, socialism, Dataism and to neuralconsciousness of the super computer today. When Alexa came into market it revealed that not the human learn the technology rather computer learns the human technology and replace humans. It creates collaboration among computers and humans, free people and increase trust between the human and the machine. It enables in decision making, planning and creates wellness for the humans. It works efficiently in the war zones, defense, hospitals, hotels and other fields today. Similarly philosophy too evolves in its thinking pattern.

In pre-modern period, philosophers like Thales focused on the reality of the universe. Parmenides said reality never changes and Heraclitus said all changes. The classic philosophers

began to reflect on body and soul. Descartes famous quote, "Cogito ergo sum" began to think on self and end in Hegel's idea. Einstein says, "God does not play dice" so it broke down MPN absolutism. So the reality becomes relative by relativity theory and thereby uncertainty principles, Quantum, Quarks, waves of Heisenberg and god particles of Higgs Boson at hand now. Finally from the cosmic perspective to machine evolution led chaos in human consciousness. Hence, the reality in search is in competitive world but the situations of people's hope in anguish, deep seated changes, changes in social order, changes in attitudes, morals and religion, imbalances, broader aspirations of mankind and man's deeper questionings are entangled with dichotomy. So what is human? What are all achievements that eradicated the sufferings today? (GS.1965, 795-800) GS describes that discoveries and their might men are troubled today and perplexed by questions about current trends of super power AI in the world, their role and place in the universe and the destiny of human nature. Hence, the church offers service to human kind in solidarity to enter into dialogue and solve human problems in best possible way along with thinkers and theologians. Pope Francis is on his way synodal journey focusing on dialogue which opens new ways for the 'Gospel peace', 'social dialogue for peace' global unity and protection (Eph6:15, ND: EG, 2013, 1049 & LS, 2015, 1051) This dialogical attempt had been made true by the theological dialogue between Bishop T. Dabre and Francis Gonsalves, president JDV, Pune on August 17, 2020 to build a new world of love, service and sacrifice to the humanity.

Legal and Ethical Perspectives

The continuous dialogue at every level must lead the civil authorities around the world and consider it as grave duty to acknowledge the true nature of family to protect, foster, safeguard public morality and promote domestic prosperity world at large. The members have the freedom to establish family and nurture moral values and religious conviction and have the freedom to

profess their faith and hand it over to the other members of the extended families in the society .They have right to private property, to free enterprise, to obtain work, and right to emigrate, right to medical care and other benefits and associate their fellow families and to have representation before the civil authority (CCC, 2210-2211, 533-534, GS 52, no. 2)

According to Harari ethics and morality cannot get from the nature. If we go against the nature then it is unnatural. What we have to observe is that whether the nature cause suffering or not. Similarly killing humans and animals for experiments on genetic engineering, neuron engineering and humanoids process are not ethical according to the dogma of the Catholic Church. GS 16 says that we discover a law which we have not laid upon ourselves but we obey. John Paul II says in *Veritatis Splendour* (VS 10-14, 1993) that morality is ‘universal call to perfection’. So we need to have proper relation to humans, nature and the creator because it is created for the wholeness of the humans (GS16, 1965) so the nature has its ethical and natural right to protect from harmful technology which causes danger to it.

AI Exploitation and human’s unconsciousness

AI exploits the species in the name of experiments. The brain computer interface can resurrect extinct species by DNA samples by genetic engineering. Machines diagnosis, prescribes medicines, updates information, used in drone monitoring system, printing basic organs, error free and efficient in surgery than humans, autonomous cars, supersonic aircraft, robots everyday tasks, decision making, planning organizing and networks with human and machine, also annihilates human privacy, controls, monitors and we are in total surveillance. It also can kill people. Machine decides whom to offer loans and jobs. Biased and fallible algorithms play role of black and white system. We need to understand the technological exploitation and our ethical response in the

society at large. We are not mere citizen rather must become judge on ‘what it is’ and ‘what it ought to be’ and ‘what is right to permit to happen’ says Polkinghorne (Polkinghorne, 2014, 43) Stephen Jayard says in his talk on July 26, 2020 that ‘we need to grow in God’s wisdom and discerning spirit to know what is good and evil. Schilling says ‘faith seeks reason’. He sees the parallel between ‘way of God and way of science’ (Schilling, 1973, 197) we need to apprehend this ethical consciousness today.

Conclusion

AI technology in 21st century is shaking the existential crisis of humans, environment, socio-economic, climate changes, inequality and others says F. Capra. Similarly social, religious, political, philosophical and other levels too. Humans experience the systemic problems which need to be modified for a paradigm by the system in which it created so far. The systemic view of this dangerous technology must be scrutinized of this binary thinking inline with human patterns, relationship and the context. So the religions, mystics and other thinkers must understand the foundational experience of the reality of humans and frame guidelines for the well beings of the members as we use modern technology. As for as Christians we need to follow the ethical guidelines with regard to AI for everyone’s dignity, well being and build the kingdom of God. Let us give life to the existing dogmas in to praxis for the global protection. Well being either leads to Humanizing Machine or Mechanizing Human.

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